

EVALUATING THE EFFECT OF VITAMIN D DEFICIENCY ON FASTING LIPID PROFILE AND ATHEROGENIC INDEX OF PLASMA

Rabia Rasheed¹, Muhammad Anees Sharif², Umama Sharif³, Memona Shabbir⁴, Amina Asif⁵

^{1,3,4,5}B.Sc Medical Laboratory Technology students, Punjab Institute of Cardiology, Lahore

²Pathology Technologist, Punjab Institute of Cardiology, Lahore

¹rabiahira315@gmail.com, ²anees.sharif2@gmail.com, ³umamasharif20@gmail.com,

⁴memonashabbir92@gmail.com, ⁵amnahasif@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17708358>

Keywords

Vitamin D deficiency, Lipid Profile, Atherogenic Index of plasma, Cardiovascular Health

Article History

Received: 05 October 2025

Accepted: 13 November 2025

Published: 25 November 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Rabia Rasheed

Abstract

Objective:

To determine the effect on vitamin D deficiency on lipid metabolism and cardiovascular health assessed through Atherogenic index of plasma

Methodology

This cross-sectional prospective study was conducted on 147 individuals over a span of five months at a tertiary care laboratory. 3 mL fasting sample of individuals was drawn and subjected to test vitamin D levels, fasting lipid profile (triglycerides, total cholesterol, low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C), very low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (VLDL-C) or high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C)) and Atherogenic index of plasma was calculated to assess the cardiovascular risk. Pearson's correlation was applied to test the correlation between vitamin D levels and triglycerides, total cholesterol, LDL-C, VLDL-C, HDL-C and Atherogenic index of plasma. All these parameters were compared in vitamin D deficient and sufficient group using independent T-test and were noted as mean \pm S.D.

Results

Out of 147 individuals, 82 individuals were deficient in vitamin D ($<30\text{ng/mL}$) while 65 individuals had optimum vitamin D levels ($>30\text{ng/mL}$). Pearson's correlation of vitamin D showed weak positive correlation with triglycerides ($r = 0.021$, $p = 0.803$), total cholesterol ($r = 0.014$, $p = 0.871$), HDL ($r = 0.095$, $p = 0.253$) and VLDL ($r = 0.021$, $p = 0.803$), while a weak negative correlation with LDL-C ($r = -0.05$, $p = 0.544$) and Atherogenic index of plasma ($r = -0.069$, $p = 0.404$). Vitamin D showed statistically non-significant correlation ($p < 0.05$) with all parameters these parameters. Only total cholesterol and LDL-C levels differ significantly in vitamin D deficient and sufficient groups, ($p = 0.030$), ($p = 0.015$) respectively.

Conclusion

Vitamin D deficiency leads to significantly raised cholesterol and LDL-C components of lipid profile while other components such as triglycerides, HDL-C, VLDL-C showed no significant changes with vitamin D deficiency. Vitamin D deficiency had a little effect on the Atherogenic index of plasma

INTRODUCTION

Vitamin D is a fat-soluble vitamin that functions like a hormone and is crucial in the mineralization of bones and musculoskeletal health maintenance.¹ The physiological role of vitamin D extends to immunity, endocrine function, glucose metabolism and supporting cardiovascular health.² The presence of Vitamin D receptors (VDRs) and the enzyme 1-alpha-hydroxylase in various tissues enables vitamin D to regulate a wide range of biological activities.³

Vitamin D deficiency has become a global health is and significantly prevalent in populations across geographical regions. This widespread insufficiency is alarming because low levels of vitamin D are linked to numerous adverse health outcomes that include dyslipidemia and elevated cardiovascular risk.⁴

Dyslipidemia, defined as abnormalities in lipid parameters such as either elevated triglycerides, total cholesterol, low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C), very low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (VLDL-C) or decreased high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C), is a known contributor to coronary artery disease.⁵ The potential interaction between vitamin D levels and lipid metabolism calls for thorough investigation. Vitamin D levels influence lipid profiles through various mechanisms, particularly its involvement in modulating inflammation and improving insulin sensitivity.^{6,7} Moreover, the impact of vitamin D on lipid parameters remains a subject of interest with some studies indicating a potential association while others reporting inconclusive findings.

These discrepancies highlight the need to define nature and extent of the association between vitamin D deficiency and cardiovascular risk. The risk to cardiovascular health is assessed through the Atherogenic index of plasma (AIP), which is an easy and reliable marker to determine the risk of cardiovascular health. This study aims to evaluate the effect of vitamin D deficiency on fasting lipid profiles and the Atherogenic index of

plasma. This study will contribute significantly to a comprehensive understanding the role of vitamin D in cardiovascular health.

Materials and Methodology

This cross sectional observational study was conducted at the tertiary care laboratory from April, 2025 to August, 2025. A total of 147 individuals were recruited in our study according to consecutive sampling technique. Eligibility was determined based on predefined inclusion criteria inclusion criteria i.e. age >18 years, no history of taking lipid lowering drugs, no history of vitamin D supplementations in 3 months and proper fasting of 8 to 12 hours. Individual not meeting the above mentioned criteria were excluded from the study.

3mL blood was drawn in the Lithium Heparin vial and vitamin D₃, triglycerides, total cholesterol, HDL-C, were analyzed using ARCHITECT i1000SR (Abbott Laboratories, Chicago, IL, USA). Results of each patients were verified against internal quality control to ensure analytical accuracy. LDL-C was calculated using the formula $LDL-C = Total\ Cholesterol - (HDL-C + Triglycerides/5)$, VLDL-C was calculated using $Triglycerides/5$ and Atherogenic index of plasma was calculated using equation: $\log_{10}(HDL-C/Triglycerides)$. Participant were classified into two groups: Group A: participants with vitamin D >30ng/mL; Group B: participants with vitamin D <30ng/mL

Pearson's correlation was performed between vitamin D and triglycerides, total cholesterol, HDL-C, LDL-C, VLDL-C and Atherogenic index of plasma, *p*-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant. Independent T-test was applied to evaluate biochemical differences between both groups. All data was analyzed using statistical package for social sciences SPSS version 26.0.

Results

Our study population consisted of 147 individuals and the mean age of our study population was 48.25 ± 11.2 years. Majority of the study population ($n=63$, 43%) fell between 44 to 57 years of age

Age group	Number of participants
18-30 years	11
31-43 years	40
44-57 years	63
>57 years	33
Total participants	147

Pearson correlation of vitamin D showed weak positive correlation with triglycerides ($r = 0.021$, $p = 0.803$), total cholesterol ($r = 0.014$, $p = 0.871$), HDL ($r = 0.095$, $p = 0.253$) and VLDL ($r = 0.021$, $p = 0.803$), while a weak negative correlation with LDL-C ($r = -0.05$, $p = 0.544$) and Atherogenic index of plasma ($r = -0.069$, $p = 0.404$). Vitamin D showed statistically non-significant correlation ($p < 0.05$) with all parameters including triglycerides, total cholesterol, LDL-C, HDL-C, VLDL-C and Atherogenic index of plasma.

Parameters	r-value	p-value
Triglycerides	0.021	0.803
Total Cholesterol	0.014	0.871
LDL-C	-0.05	0.544
HDL-C	0.095	0.253
VLDL-C	0.021	0.803
Atherogenic index of plasma	-0.069	0.404

Out of 147 individuals, 82 (56%) had vitamin D deficiency i.e., vitamin D <30 ng/mL while 65 (34%) had sufficient vitamin D level i.e., vitamin D >30 ng/mL. In the vitamin deficient group, 62 individuals (79%), and 20 individuals (21%) showed deranged and normal lipid profiles respectively. In the vitamin sufficient group, 34 individuals (56%) showed deranged lipid profiles.

	Deranged lipid profile	Normal lipid profile	Total
Vitamin D deficiency	62	20	82
Vitamin D sufficiency	34	31	65
Total	96	51	147

Our study population was divided in 2 group on the basis of vitamin D levels, group A had population with sufficient vitamin D while group B had population with sufficient vitamin D levels. Independent t-test was applied to compare mean \pm SD of triglycerides, total cholesterol, LDL-C, HDL-C, VLDL-C and Atherogenic index of plasma in both groups that are enlisted in table 4.

	<u>Vit D deficient group</u> (n=82)	<u>Vit D sufficient group</u> (n=65)	p-value
Triglycerides (mmol/L)	2.077 \pm 1.09	2.05 \pm 1.07	0.438 ^{NS}
Total Cholesterol (mmol/L)	4.96 \pm 0.93	4.82 \pm 1.09	0.030 ^S

LDLC (mmol/L)	3.26±0.88	3.04±0.88	0.015 ^S
HDL-C (mmol/L)	1.08±0.37	1.09±0.25	0.946 ^{NS}
VLDL-C (mmol/L)	0.95±0.51	0.94±0.43	0.438 ^{NS}
Atherogenic index of plasma	0.25±0.24	0.22±0.28	0.213 ^{NS}

Discussion

Vitamin D deficiency is increasingly known for its contribution to metabolic and cardiovascular disturbances, far beyond its role in bone and mineral homeostasis. In this study cohort of 147 participants, we investigated the association between vitamin D status and parameters of the fasting lipid profile, along with the Atherogenic index of plasma (AIP), to better understand the metabolic implications of vitamin D deficiency. Pearson’s correlation analysis did not reveal a statistically significant correlation between serum vitamin D levels and markers of lipid profile.

Participants were grouped into vitamin D-deficient and vitamin D-sufficient groups, and lipid profile parameters including triglycerides, total cholesterol, LDL-C, HDL-C, VLDL-C, and Atherogenic index of plasma of both groups were analyzed. The comparison between groups provided us an important insight into how vitamin D deficiency affects metabolic processes.

A noteworthy finding of this study was the disproportionately high frequency of deranged lipid profile among vitamin D-deficient individuals. Out of 82 participants in vitamin D-deficient group, 62 (79%) had deranged lipid profile, on the other hand among vitamin D-sufficient individuals, only 34 (56%) had lipid abnormalities. This difference suggests that vitamin D deficiency may predispose individuals to lipid disturbances even in the absence of strong statistical correlations across all lipid parameters.⁸ The elevated occurrence of dyslipidemia in the deficient group aligns with the physiological understanding that vitamin D plays a regulatory role in lipid metabolism through multiple pathways, including modulation of parathyroid hormone activity, reduction of chronic

inflammation, improvement of insulin sensitivity, and influence on hepatic

lipid synthesis. Low vitamin D levels may impair these processes, ultimately contributing to less favorable lipid profiles.^{9,10}

In our study, total cholesterol and LDL-C levels were found to be significantly higher in the vitamin D-deficient group ($p < 0.05$). This suggests that vitamin D deficiency may particularly influence cholesterol patterns and promotes an atherogenic lipid pattern.¹¹ Several mechanisms support this observation, such as expression of Vitamin D receptors in hepatocytes regulate genes linked to cholesterol synthesis and clearance.¹² Thus, vitamin D deficiency may reduce LDL-C receptor expression and impair LDL-C uptake from circulation.¹³ Vitamin D is also known to enhance insulin sensitivity, and its deficiency causes insulin resistance, which alters lipid metabolism and ultimately increases hepatic cholesterol output.¹⁴

Triglycerides, HDL-C, VLDL-C, and the Atherogenic index of plasma did not show statistically significant differences between the vitamin D-deficient and vitamin D-sufficient groups. This observation suggests that vitamin D plays a more substantial role modulating the cholesterol metabolism than on triglyceride metabolism or HDL-C regulation.¹⁵

Although the Atherogenic index of plasma did not differ significantly between groups 0.25±0.24 and 0.22±0.28, (p -value 0.213). The Atherogenic index of plasma remained within a borderline to high-risk range in both populations. A study by **Kazemian *et al.***, reported that the relationship between vitamin D and lipid metabolism is influenced by many confounding factors such as

genetic variations, dietary habits, physical activity, BMI, and hormonal status of individuals.¹⁶ All these observations suggest that an overall elevated cardiovascular risk is influenced by factors beyond vitamin D status alone.¹⁷

Conclusion

From this study, it is concluded that vitamin D deficiency is associated with significantly elevated total cholesterol and LDL-C levels, suggesting a

more atherogenic lipid profile among the vitamin D-deficient individuals. Although triglycerides, HDL-C, VLDL-C and the Atherogenic index of plasma did not show significant differences, the exceptionally high occurrence of dyslipidemia among vitamin D-deficient participants highlight the importance of evaluating vitamin D status as part of metabolic and cardiovascular risk assessment.

References

1. Li H, Cao W, Tao L, Zhu Y. The role of fat-soluble vitamins on bone metabolism and osteoporosis: a literature review. *Annals of Medicine*. 2025 Dec 31;57(1):2533429.
2. Dey SK, Kumar S, Rani D, Maurya SK, Banerjee P, Verma M, Senapati S. Implications of vitamin D deficiency in systemic inflammation and cardiovascular health. *Critical reviews in food science and nutrition*. 2024 Nov 5;64(28):10438-55.
3. Bikle DD. Vitamin D biochemistry and physiology. In *Extraskeletal Effects of Vitamin D: A Clinical Guide 2018* Apr 24 (pp. 1-40). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
4. Kheiri B, Abdalla A, Osman M, Ahmed S, Hassan M, Bachuwa G. Vitamin D deficiency and risk of cardiovascular diseases: a narrative review. *Clinical hypertension*. 2018 Jun 22;24(1):9.
5. Tall AR, Thomas DG, Gonzalez-Cabodevilla AG, Goldberg IJ. Addressing dyslipidemic risk beyond LDL-cholesterol. *The Journal of clinical investigation*. 2022 Jan 4;132(1).
6. Surdu AM, Pinzariu O, Ciobanu DM, Negru AG, Căinap SS, Lazea C, Iacob D, Săraci G, Tirinescu D, Borda IM, Cismaru G. Vitamin D and its role in the lipid metabolism and the development of atherosclerosis. *Biomedicines*. 2021 Feb 9;9(2):172.
7. Argano C, Mirarchi L, Amodeo S, Orlando V, Torres A, Corrao S. The role of vitamin D and its molecular bases in insulin resistance, diabetes, metabolic syndrome, and cardiovascular disease: state of the art. *International journal of molecular sciences*. 2023 Oct 23;24(20):15485.
8. Wang Y, Si S, Liu J, Wang Z, Jia H, Feng K, Sun L, Song SJ. The associations of serum lipids with vitamin D status. *PloS one*. 2016 Oct 21;11(10):e0165157.
9. Barchetta I, Cimini FA, Cavallo MG. Vitamin D and metabolic dysfunction-associated fatty liver disease (MAFLD): an update. *Nutrients*. 2020 Oct 28;12(11):3302.
10. Danese VC, Pepe J, Ferrone F, Colangelo L, De Martino V, Nieddu L, Ferrazza G, Panzini E, Pascone R, Blocki F, Minisola S. The mutual interplay between bone, glucose and lipid metabolism: The role of vitamin D and PTH. *Nutrients*. 2023 Jun 30;15(13):2998.
11. Warren T, McAllister R, Morgan A, Rai TS, McGilligan V, Ennis M, Page C, Kelly C, Peace A, Corfe BM, Mc Auley M. The interdependency and co-regulation of the vitamin D and cholesterol metabolism. *Cells*. 2021 Aug 6;10(8):2007.
12. Bozic M, Guzmán C, Benet M, Sánchez-Campos S, García-Monzón C, Gari E, Gatiús S, Valdivielso JM, Jover R. Hepatocyte vitamin D receptor regulates lipid metabolism and mediates

- experimental diet-induced steatosis. *Journal of hepatology*. 2016 Oct 1;65(4):748-57.
- ^{13.} Li S, He Y, Lin S, Hao L, Ye Y, Lv L, Sun Z, Fan H, Shi Z, Li J, Feng R. Increase of circulating cholesterol in vitamin D deficiency is linked to reduced vitamin D receptor activity via the Insig-2/SREBP-2 pathway. *Molecular nutrition & food research*. 2016 Apr;60(4):798-809.
 - ^{14.} Argano C, Mirarchi L, Amodeo S, Orlando V, Torres A, Corrao S. The role of vitamin D and its molecular bases in insulin resistance, diabetes, metabolic syndrome, and cardiovascular disease: state of the art. *International journal of molecular sciences*. 2023 Oct 23;24(20):15485.
 - ^{15.} Surdu AM, Pinzariu O, Ciobanu DM, Negru AG, Căinap SS, Lazea C, Iacob D, Săraci G, Tirinescu D, Borda IM, Cismaru G. Vitamin D and its role in the lipid metabolism and the development of atherosclerosis. *Biomedicines*. 2021 Feb 9;9(2):172.
 - ^{16.} Kazemian E, Amouzegar A, Akbari ME, Moradi N, Gharibzadeh S, Jamshidi-Naeini Y, Khademolmele M, As'habi A, Davoodi SH. Vitamin D receptor gene polymorphisms affecting changes in visceral fat, waist circumference and lipid profile in breast cancer survivors supplemented with vitamin D3. *Lipids in health and disease*. 2019 Aug 9;18(1):161.
 - ^{17.} Lioy B, Webb RJ, Amirabdollahian F. The association between the atherogenic index of plasma and cardiometabolic risk factors: a review. *InHealthcare* 2023 Mar 28 (Vol. 11, No. 7, p. 966). MDPI.